

Introduction

Extraction is the most common consequence of cracks in endodontically treated teeth. In the traditional endodontic access cavity, the concept of “extension for prevention” in endodontic access is followed to facilitate the procedure with no dentin interfering to obtain a straight-line access. The preparation of the endodontic access cavity, following the TEC principals, were reported to be the second-largest cause of tooth structure loss and failure of endodontic treatment. According to some authors, the modification of traditional endodontic therapy with accurate access cavities, which protect the structure of the crucial dentin, may benefit the functional integrity, fracture resistance, and overall prognosis of teeth. Clark and Khademi have developed a novel approach to cavity preparation termed minimally invasive access, inspired by the concept of minimally invasive dentistry. Contracted endodontic cavities (CECs), which were inspired by the concepts of MIE, emphasize endodontically treated tooth structure preservation, including preserves part of the pulp chamber roof and pericervical dentin (PCD). Precervical dentin refers to the tooth substance 4 mm above and 4 mm apical to the alveolar bone crest. The preservation of PCD is important for dental structure and is associated with a long-term survival benefit. ‘Silva et al’ classified endodontic access cavities into 6 main categories, which are (i) traditional access cavity, (ii) conservative access cavity, (iii) ultraconservative access cavity, (iv) truss access cavity, (v) caries-driven access cavity, and (vi) restorative-driven access cavity (Figure1). The availability of nickel-titanium (NiTi) engine-driven instruments, OM, ultrasonic instruments and CBCT has made the MIEC approach potentially feasible in clinical endodontics.

Materials & Methods

An electronic search of studies published in the English language in PUBMED, SCOPUS, SCIENCE DIRECT, and GOOGLE SCHOLAR from December 2017 to December 2023 was conducted using the keywords; “contracted access cavities”, “endodontic access cavity”, “fracture resistance”, “minimally invasive access cavities”, “traditional access cavities”. A total of 101 articles were included in title and abstract screening. After application of exclusion and inclusion criteria a total of 15 articles were included in this review.

Results

Jiang et al. compared the biomechanical properties of first maxillary molars with different endodontic cavities through finite element analysis. They concluded that CECs, which maintained a larger amount of coronal hard tissue, could reduce stress distribution on cervical structures and provide better fracture resistance. They also showed a dramatic stress increase on the pericervical dentin when the access cavity became larger. Krishan et al. also found that CECs for mandibular molars and premolars may improve fracture resistance. However, the fracture resistance of the teeth was tested without filling and restoration. In another study, Plotino et al. reached a similar conclusion that TECs showed lower fracture strength than CECs and NECs in maxillary and mandibular premolars and molars. They also added that NECs do not differ from CECs in terms of fracture resistance. Rover et al. and Moore et al. evaluated the influence of CECs in maxillary molars and they showed no statistically significant differences between TECs and CECs in terms of fracture resistance. In accordance with those studies, Silva et al. conducted a systematic review of in vitro studies evaluating the impact of CECs on fracture resistance and found no proof that supports the use of CECs over TECs. They concluded that the influence of access cavity design on fracture resistance remains a controversial issue. The variability of the research methodology and the limited number of studies could account for the conflicting data in the literature.

Figure 1: Classification of different types of access cavity designs of anterior and posterior teeth

Discussion

The biomechanical behavior of ETT is dependent on the remaining amount of sound coronal and radicular tooth structures. The contracted endodontic cavity (CEC) was suggested to preserve the pericervical dentine by incomplete deroofting of the pulp chamber. Though some studies demonstrated that the contracted endodontic cavities (CECs) approach improves the fracture resistance of teeth comparing to those treated by a traditional endodontic cavity, some other studies displayed no significant difference in fracture strength between CEAs and TEAs. Different designed methodologies might be the reason for these inconsistent results, for instance; the use of different restoration materials, the kind of assessed teeth, and methodological complications related to the fracture test design. Some authors speculate that preservation of the soffit and PCD might not always be possible when the carious lesion or existing cavity has already jeopardized the structural integrity of the teeth in these critical areas, hindering the application of CEC. Moreover, there are some concerns associated with CEC including; the ability of canal detection and negotiation, the quality of chemo-mechanical preparation, obturation and post-endodontic restoration, increased iatrogenic mishaps, canal transportation consequential to unwanted straightening of the canal curvature, canal perforation and apical extrusion, negative effects on the aesthetic outcome, and prolonged treatment time (generally technically challenging and demands advanced skills and experience). It should be noted that in vitro studies have limitations and their results should be interpreted with caution. Load bearing capability of endodontically treated teeth is affected by several factors such as the number of adjacent teeth, the number of occlusal contacts, the position of the tooth in a dental arch, and the apical status of the teeth, which cannot be simulated in vitro. The method of loading in vitro is also different from the oral clinical setting because the load is static in vitro while it is dynamic in vivo. More in vitro studies must be carried out before planning clinical studies. Furthermore, randomized controlled trials and retrospective and prospective studies need to be conducted before these new methods are widely accepted. The application of CECs in clinical practice needs critical consideration by deliberating the benefits and risks of the CECs and TECs.

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